

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing

Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Evaluating Collaborative Filtering Models
in Music Recommender Systems:
Enhancing Diversity and Long-Tail Metrics
with a Multi-Stakeholder Approach

Diana Tyman Rondiak

Supervisor: Xavier Serra

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Dedication

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the challenges and opportunities in enhancing fairness, diversity and long-tail content coverage in music recommender systems from a multi-stakeholder perspective. Music streaming platforms are pivotal in shaping music discovery, and the recommendations generated by these systems significantly impact user satisfaction as well as the visibility and success of artists. In this study, two collaborative filtering models are developed and evaluated: a simple model representing traditional approaches and an enhanced model incorporating advanced techniques such as diversity ranking and long-tail promotion. These enhancements aim to address the limitations of conventional music recommender systems, which often favour popular content, thereby reducing the diversity of recommendations. The effectiveness of these models is assessed using the metrics: Aggregate Diversity, Long-Tail Coverage and User Popularity Deviation. The results demonstrate that the enhanced model significantly improves diversity and long-tail coverage, suggesting its potential to offer more equitable and varied recommendations. However, the findings also highlight the complexity of balancing these improvements with user satisfaction, as increased diversity sometimes comes at the expense of relevance and personalization. This research underscores the importance of considering multiple stakeholders in the design of ethical and effective music recommendation systems. The study advocates for moving beyond user-centred approaches to include the perspectives of artists and platforms, thereby fostering a more balanced and inclusive ecosystem.

Keywords: music recommender systems; collaborative filtering; diversity.

1. Introduction

1.1. Recommender Systems

Recommender Systems (RS) have become indispensable tools in navigating the vast and complex information spaces we encounter daily. These systems filter large databases of items to present users with the most relevant content, whether it's movies to watch, books to read or even financial products like mortgages. The primary function of a RS is to maximize utility and relevance for the user, often using a blend of techniques from machine learning, user modeling and data management.

According to Resnik and Varian (Resnick & Varian, 1997), "*In a typical recommender system, people provide recommendations as inputs, which the system then aggregates and directs to appropriate recipients. In some cases, the primary transformation is in the aggregation; in others, the system's value lies in its ability to make good matches between the recommenders and those seeking recommendations.*" This early definition captures the core purpose of RS, to connect users with content that best matches their preferences and needs.

While the basic principles of RS remain consistent across domains, the specifics can vary significantly depending on the application. For example, on platforms like Amazon¹, recommendations are often driven by item-based collaborative filtering, where products are suggested based on similar items that other users have purchased together. In contrast, entertainment-based RS, such as those used for music, movies and books, must account for more complex user behaviors, such as personal tastes, habits and evolving preferences.

1.1.1 Recommender Systems in Music

The application of RS in music has a rich history, dating back to the early 2000s with the emergence of digital music libraries. Early systems like Pandora's Music Genome

¹ <https://www.amazon.com/>

Project² and Last.fm's³ collaborative filtering models were pioneering in their approach to personalized music discovery. Pandora focused on detailed musical attributes , while Last.fm leveraged user-generated data to create tailored playlists.

The landscape of music recommendation has evolved significantly with the advent of streaming services such as Spotify⁴ and Deezer⁵. These platforms have democratized access to music, enabling users to explore vast catalogs with ease. Consequently, the role of RS has become even more crucial, as they help listeners navigate these extensive collections by providing personalized suggestions that align with their individual tastes.

However, the influence of RS in music extends beyond user satisfaction. The recommendations made by these systems have profound implications for artists' careers. According to a 2020 Billboard article⁶, 62% of people cited streaming services as their primary source of music discovery, surpassing traditional methods like recommendations from friends and family . Furthermore, AI-driven recommendations account for about 30% of all streams on Spotify⁷, underscoring the significant role these systems play in shaping music consumption.

Yet, this influence is a double-edged sword. The same algorithms that help popularize certain artists can also perpetuate inequalities within the industry. A report from Rolling Stone⁸ revealed that the top 1% of artists on streaming platforms account for an overwhelming share of streams, showing a big gap in wealth and exposure. Recommender systems often favor these well-established artists within mainstream genres, further marginalizing independent or niche artists. This raises critical concerns about diversity, representation, and fairness in music recommendations.

² <https://www.pandora.com/about/mgp>

³ <https://www.last.fm/about/trackmymusic>

⁴ <https://open.spotify.com/>

⁵ <https://www.deezer.com/en/>

⁶ https://www.musicbusinessworldwide.com/files/2021/01/MRC_Billboard_YEAR_END_2020_US-Final.pdf

⁷ <https://distributionstrategy.com/how-spotify-uses-ai-to-create-an-ultra-personalized-customer-experience-and-what-distributors-can-learn-from-it/>

⁸ <https://www.rollingstone.com/pro/news/top-1-percent-streaming-1055005/>

1.1.2 Multiple-Stakeholders in Music Recommender Systems

The complexities of RS in music are further compounded by the diverse interests of multiple stakeholders involved in the music streaming ecosystem. These stakeholders include:

- **Item Consumers or Users:** Users are the recipients of the recommendations and the primary consumers of content. Their preferences, listening habits and engagement patterns drive the recommendations.
- **Item Providers or Artists and Record Labels:** Artists and record labels create the content being recommended. Their goal is to maximize exposure, streams and revenue, but the algorithms may not always align with their interests, especially for lesser-known artists who struggle to gain visibility. However, for simplicity, this thesis will focus on artists as the primary stakeholders, recognizing that record labels often share aligned interests with artists.
- **Platforms:** The streaming platforms themselves are responsible for developing and implementing the recommendation algorithms. Their objectives include maximizing user engagement, retaining subscribers and optimizing revenue. However, these goals may not always align with the fair representation of all artists or the diverse preferences of users.

The friction between these stakeholders highlights the need for a balanced approach to designing RS in music. As platforms increasingly rely on AI to manage and distribute content, the potential for misalignment and power imbalances grows. For example, the rise of AI-generated music, often inserted into playlists without proper attribution, introduces new challenges for fairness and transparency in music recommendations⁹. This underscores the importance of ongoing research into how RS can be designed to fairly serve all stakeholders involved.

⁹ <https://dailyai.com/2024/05/ai-generated-songs-rack-up-thousands-of-listens-on-spotify/>

1.2 Motivation

RS have become an integral part of our daily lives, guiding us in making decisions ranging from what movies to watch to which music to listen to. In the context of music streaming platforms, RS are not only about song recommendations but also about promoting the artists behind the music. These recommendations are shaped by various factors, including the user's musical preferences, geographical location and local music trends.

However, when a new user registers on a music streaming platform, the system typically generates initial playlists and song recommendations based on limited information, such as basic demographic details and the user's country of registration. This often results in a lack of personalization that does not accurately reflect the user's true musical tastes.

Despite the benefits of RS in music streaming platforms, several notable issues persist. Artist biases, wherein popular artists receive preferential treatment in promoting their new projects, pose challenges for emerging or lesser-known artists. Additionally, recent changes in royalties' payment methods by platforms like Deezer and Spotify have increased disparities, benefiting established artists more and limiting the earning potential of newer talents (Jensen, 2024).

The primary objective of this thesis is to investigate the various biases inherent in music RS on streaming platforms, while acknowledging the notion that these systems involve multiple stakeholders with different and sometimes contradictory goals or intentions. Analyzing the perspectives and interests of each stakeholder, including the platform itself, content providers and users (Burke et al., 2016), has gained attention in the research community in recent years (Abdollahpouri et al., 2020). However, much of the research in this area remains primarily focused on evaluating recommender systems from the consumers' perspective.

By investigating these challenges and seeking solutions, this thesis aims to contribute to the development of more equitable and inclusive music RS that better serve the interests of all stakeholders involved.

1.3 Objectives of the thesis

The primary objective of this thesis is to explore and enhance the diversity and long-tail coverage in music RS while considering the multi-stakeholder architecture inherent in these systems. This research aims to develop and evaluate recommendation algorithms that not only serve the users but also fairly represent the interests of artists and the platform itself. The thesis seeks to strike a balance between promoting lesser-known artists and ensuring that recommendations remain relevant and personalized for users.

To achieve these objectives, these are the research questions to be answered throughout the thesis:

- 1. In what ways can recommendation algorithms be modified to improve diversity and long-tail inclusion, and how do these modifications impact the satisfaction of different stakeholders?**
- 2. What are the trade-offs involved in enhancing diversity and long-tail coverage in music recommender systems, particularly concerning user satisfaction and platform objectives?**

1.4 General structure of the thesis

The thesis is structured into five main chapters.

The first chapter serves as the introduction, setting out the motivation, objectives, and research questions of the study. The second chapter reviews the State of the Art, presenting existing literature and previous work related to music recommender systems. The third chapter details the research methodology, including the data sources, algorithms and evaluation metrics used. In the fourth chapter, the results of the research are presented, analyzing the effectiveness of different algorithms in enhancing diversity and long-tail coverage. The fifth chapter concludes the thesis with a discussion of the findings, their implications and recommendations for future research.

Following these chapters, there are additional sections for the list of figures, list of tables and bibliography.

2. State of the Art

This chapter explores several important topics on which the thesis is based and are relevant for it. It begins by examining the fundamental concepts of music recommendation systems (RS), followed by an exploration of fairness, biases and limitations within these systems. Additionally, it introduces the concept of multi-stakeholder architecture in music RS, as well as an overall introduction to the existing metrics used to evaluate the RS. Understanding these topics is crucial for developing and implementing music RS that are both effective and equitable.

2.1. Methods for Music Recommendation Systems

There are two primary approaches to music recommendation: content-based (CB) and collaborative filtering (CF) (Ricci et al., 2022), which can be used independently or combined to create a hybrid approach.

The CB recommendation algorithm creates personalized suggestions by analyzing descriptive features from items that the user has previously interacted with, potentially reflecting their preferences and interests. The CF algorithm produces recommendations based on the engagements between the items and users to produce the recommendations. RS using the CF method rely on different types of input. The most straightforward input is explicit feedback, where users directly express their interest in items, such as rating an item on a scale of one to five stars. However, explicit feedback isn't always accessible. In such cases, other RS utilize implicit feedback, where platforms infer or make assumptions about users' preferences based on their behavior. For instance, a platform may predict products a user would like based on their browsing or listening history.

Hybrid recommender systems combine various techniques, typically incorporating the strengths of both CF and CB methods, but they can also integrate other approaches. The hybrid approach is designed to address the limitations of individual recommendation techniques. For example, CF may encounter the new-item problem, where it cannot recommend items without any ratings. However, CB is not restricted by this issue,

making it complementary to CF and enabling the creation of a more robust recommendation system.

The following figure illustrates a simple example of how CB and CF approaches function in recommender systems:

Figure 1. Example of Content-Based and Collaborative Filtering methods in Recommender Systems¹⁰

Other kinds of RS methods include context-aware method, where contextual information, such as time, place, etc., is considered other factors that are not only users and items (Ricci et al., 2022). Session-based recommender systems are specifically designed for situations where there is limited long-term user information available. These systems aim to predict the next item to be consumed based on the most recent items consumed within the current session, making them useful across a wide range of industries, including news recommendations, e-commerce and music recommendation (Ricci et al., 2022). One significant advantage of session-based recommender systems is their ability to adapt to the user's current interests, which is particularly relevant in the music domain. By focusing on the most recent items consumed, these systems can provide recommendations that are tailored to the user's current preferences, thereby improving the overall personalized experience. Furthermore, there are other kinds of RS such as

¹⁰ <https://github.com/xci/recommender-system-tutorial>

adversarial RS, group RS, natural language processing for RS and others (Ricci et al., 2022).

2.1.1. Biases and Limitations in Music RS

Considering the various methods of music recommendation discussed earlier, while these systems have proved to be successful to recommend items, it's important to acknowledge the researched limitations that impact biases and constraints in these systems.

There is a common issue in CF recommendations called the “cold start” problem. This occurs when a new user or item joins a given platform, and, as the system provides recommendations based on users’ previous interactions, if an item has no previous history, then the system will tend to recommend the most popular items. This tendency, known as long-tail or popularity bias, results in recommendation systems favoring popular or mainstream items over lesser-known ones. Consequently, users' existing preferences are reinforced, and attention remains focused on popular items, limiting exploration of the long-tail of lesser-known items (Celma Herrada, 2009).

While the previous biases can also be applied to CB RS, they are less common. However, CB methods may encounter another issue known as the novelty problem. This happens when the recommendation system consistently selects items based on the same set of characteristics. Hence, users may receive similar items repeatedly, leading to a lack of diversity in the recommendations. Similarly, the gray-sheep problem arises when users have unconventional or diverse music tastes that do not align with the system's predefined categories. As a result, it becomes challenging to recommend suitable items for these users, particularly if the system's collection is limited in size or biased towards specific genres (Celma Herrada, 2009).

2.2. Multistakeholder Recommendation Systems

Recommender systems traditionally prioritize the user experience, focusing on delivering recommendations that meet user preferences. By incorporating various forms

of feedback, both implicit and explicit, these systems continuously refine their algorithms to offer more accurate and relevant suggestions. The user-centric approach of most recommender systems is driven by their primary goal of maximizing user satisfaction and engagement. Tailored recommendations tailored to individual preferences not only encourage repeat usage but also increase the likelihood of user subscription and content consumption. This, in turn, contributes to the overall revenue of music streaming platforms through subscription fees and advertising revenue (Ferraro & Serra Casals, 2021).

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in understanding how music RS affect the various stakeholders involved. Music RS are commonly used on music streaming platforms such as Spotify, Deezer or Pandora (Abdollahpouri et al., 2020). The main stakeholders in music RS include:

- **Users (item consumers):** Users are the recipients of recommendations and consume the recommended items. They visit the platform in search of new items that meet their preferences and needs.
- **Artists and Record Labels (item providers or suppliers):** Artists and record labels serve as the providers or suppliers of the recommended content. They are responsible for creating and standing behind the recommended objects.
- **Platform:** The music streaming platform is responsible for developing and implementing the recommendation algorithm. It serves as the intermediary, matching consumers with providers.

The multistakeholder perspective can be applied in several ways within a RS:

- Evaluating the diverse interests of each stakeholder group and assessing how they are influenced by these systems.
- Implementing this perspective in the algorithm design process to optimize it and accommodate the varying objectives of each stakeholder group. This involves balancing these objectives to mitigate biases and achieve equilibrium among all parties.

- Incorporating a multistakeholder approach in the system creation phase, recognizing that the development of a music RS often involves collaboration among multiple stakeholders.

As mentioned in the previous section, for user-centric systems, there was no inclusion of feedback from suppliers and the platform, with the focus primarily on optimizing recommendations solely for user satisfaction and engagement. In contrast, in a multiple stakeholder system, feedback from all parties involved, including users, artists, record labels and the platform, is considered and integrated into the system design and evaluation processes. This approach ensures that the needs and objectives of all stakeholders are considered, leading to a more balanced and inclusive recommendation ecosystem.

The following figure illustrates a straightforward example of how various types of feedback are considered in the functionality of the recommender system:

Figure 2. User-centered schema for recommendation versus multistakeholder schema. **(a)** User-centered review of recommendation. **(b)** Multistakeholder view of recommendation. (Ricci et al., 2022)

2.2.1. User's interests

Considering that the user is one of the primary stakeholders of the RS functionality, let's revise key considerations regarding the user's interests as a stakeholder in a music RS.

One fundamental expectation of users when using a music RS is to receive music suggestions that align with their individual taste. However, the way these recommendations are presented holds significant importance. As highlighted earlier in section 2.1.1, biases can influence the recommendation process, leading to recommended songs that are either too similar in sound or mainstream. This lack of diversity in recommendations can result in a negative user experience. Therefore, it's crucial to ensure fairness and diversity in music recommendations to prevent users from encountering a lack of diversity in their suggested content (Porcaro, 2022) .

Having access to a varied selection of suggested songs allows for a broad spectrum of choices while listening to music. While there is satisfaction in enjoying familiar tunes, there is an even greater sense of enjoyment when a listener discovers an unexpected suggestion, something they wouldn't have considered looking up themselves but find positively received. This phenomenon, known as serendipity, adds a unique and enjoyable dimension to the music listening experience.

Moreover, users are not only interested in enjoying a diverse range of music but also in actively supporting their favorite or most frequently listened artists. This demonstrates a desire to contribute to the success and livelihood of these artists by streaming their music and potentially attending their concerts or purchasing merchandise. Furthermore, users often seek opportunities to discover and champion emerging artists, recognizing the importance of supporting new talent and fostering creativity within the music industry. By actively engaging with and promoting both established and emerging artists, users play a significant role in shaping the music landscape and contributing to the vibrancy of the music community.

Furthermore, increased transparency and user control in recommender systems (RS) has shown to contribute to fairness for artists (Dinnissen & Bauer, 2022). Transparency has become essential in algorithmic design, particularly in socially sensitive application areas, due to legal requirements such as the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation from the European Union, 2016) , the necessity to establish user trust in the system, the

importance of error detection to address bias and discrimination, facilitating public acceptance of new technologies and fostering accountability among platform hosts for the algorithms.

When users are provided with transparency regarding how recommendations are generated, they are more likely to appreciate the system's efforts to ensure fairness. This increased understanding leads users to value the ability to adjust preferences, provide feedback and influence the recommendations they receive, thereby contributing to a more personalized and satisfying music listening experience (Sonboli et al., 2021) .

2.2.2. Artist's interests

Nowadays, music streaming platforms serve as one of the primary sites for music consumption, making it more accessible for artists to share their music and be discovered by users on a global scale. As the main content providers for these platforms, it is important to understand what objectives and interest's artists when participating in music RS.

There is a known gap in research concerning artist's interests and perspectives regarding recommender systems (Bauer, 2020), Andrés Ferraro (Ferraro & Serra Casals, 2021) conducted a series of interviews with artists to understand their perspectives as providers on music streaming platforms and the impact of music RS on their careers.

The interviewed artists emphasize the importance of promoting diverse content on music platforms. They feel that current RS often lack the ability to highlight a wide range of musical genres and artists, leading to a homogenized listening experience. Many artists express a desire for platforms to include more diverse recommendations, ensuring that users are exposed to a broader spectrum of music beyond the mainstream. This explains the popularity bias which not only limits exposure for new talent but also stifles the growth of diverse musical expressions, and most artists agree that RS should prioritize new and lesser-known artists to provide them with a fair chance of being discovered.

This is also tied with artists being concerned about RS influencing users listening habits, if a user is used to listen to what the platform recommends them, the user won't make an active effort to research new artists or recently released music to diversify their

listening history. That is why it is important to not only tackle these biases but also to obtain more information on how these platforms make the recommendations. By understanding these mechanisms, artists believe they can better navigate the system and potentially improve their visibility. Artists hold platforms responsible for addressing and correcting any biases, whether commercial or personal. They highlight the need for fairness, particularly regarding gender representation, noting the underrepresentation of female artists in recommendations. There is also a push for RS to promote local talent, still considering that users should be free to discover music from regions different to where they live.

Despite the ease of accessing music today, discovering new artists remains challenging. For example, the "cold start" problem, where new users with no listening history are primarily exposed to popular music. They suggest that platforms should implement features to introduce new users to lesser-known artists to diversify their musical exposure. Artists express a preference for their latest releases to be more prominently featured than their older hits. They feel more connected to their recent work and believe it should be given more visibility. This approach can help keep the content on music platforms fresh and relevant.

Additional research underscores the importance of incorporating artists' interests into the development of music recommender systems, as these systems significantly impact their careers (Bauer, 2020.; Ferraro et al., 2021).

Furthermore, it is important to address the dissatisfaction with the current royalty distribution models on music platforms. Artists believe that the platforms' commercial interests often overshadow the fair treatment of creators, particularly smaller or independent ones. They call for more equitable royalty systems that accurately reflect their contributions. Given that streaming platforms generate 67% of the industry's revenue in most markets (IFPI, 2023), artists and labels, especially independent ones, have criticized the remuneration system of these platforms. This debate intensified during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, as the absence of live touring due to safety measures forced artists to rely on streaming platforms as their primary revenue source (Liang & Mao, 2022). This situation accentuated the inadequacies of the current royalty system in adequately compensating artists and rights holders for their contributions.

In addition, in 2023, two major music streaming platforms, Spotify and Deezer, changed their royalty payment systems, causing significant dissatisfaction among smaller artists and music labels (Jensen, 2024). Deezer introduced a new 'artist-centric' payment system, developed in collaboration with Universal Music Group, with plans to expand it to other major labels. This system assigns double value to streams for 'professional artists,' meaning artists with more than 1,000 monthly streams by at least 500 different listeners will receive double the credit for their streams. Additionally, streams will count double if the user actively chooses to listen to the song, rather than having it recommended by an algorithm (Deezer, 2023).

Similarly, Spotify announced they will "modernize their royalty system" by working in collaboration with artists and their teams, independent and major labels, and distributors. They introduced new policies to prevent artificial streaming, better distribute small payments that are not reaching artists, and limit those attempting to manipulate the system with noise. To generate recorded royalties, artists' tracks need to have reached over 1,000 streams in the previous 12 months. Spotify mentioned that they will not profit from tracks that do not reach that threshold; instead, they will redistribute the funds to tracks that do. Additionally, to avoid fraud, Spotify will lengthen the minimum time a track needs to be listened to generate royalties from 30 seconds to 2 minutes (Spotify, 2023).

In summary, artists have several key concerns and suggestions regarding music RS. They advocate for better mechanisms to promote local artists and ensure fair representation of female artists. They emphasize the need to support emerging artists by avoiding popularity bias and giving new artists a fair chance. Artists desire more control over recommendations and transparency in algorithmic operations, stressing that platforms should not unduly influence users' musical preferences. Providing context for songs is seen as beneficial for enhancing listener connection. There are mixed opinions on quotas as a solution for promoting local music, with no clear consensus on how to operationalize increased diversity in recommendations. Ultimately, artists agree that there should be space in music recommendations to promote new artists, but opinions vary on how to achieve this balance. Most artists also agree that the discovery of new music should be user-controlled, with transparency from platforms about how

recommendations are made and how artists can improve their visibility. These insights highlight the need for music platforms to consider the multifaceted interests of artists, ensuring that recommender systems are fair, transparent, and supportive of a diverse music ecosystem.

2.2.3. Platform's interests

Music streaming platform owners manage and maintain music RS, as well as other aspects related to running a successful music streaming service, such as marketing strategies, customer support and licensing agreements. These stakeholders play a crucial role in the development of music RS and ensuring that the system operates seamlessly to meet the needs of both users and item providers.

Generally, there's limited public information available about the inner workings of most music streaming platforms. Consequently, it's challenging to determine the specific objectives and interests that guide these platforms in the design and programming of their music RS. We can infer certain patterns within their RS, such as if they present popularity bias, gender imbalance or a prevalence of white artists. The rest of this subchapter investigates the features and values these platforms exhibit through their online presence.

Some popular music streaming platforms, such as Spotify, Deezer, Pandora, Apple Music¹¹ and YouTube Music¹², provide more than just access to their music and podcast services on their main pages. They also offer additional resources to share news and updates about their platforms, allowing other stakeholders to understand the platforms' general objectives and interests.

YouTube, Pandora, and Spotify all provide user-engaging websites, featuring community spaces where stakeholders can share doubts, questions and suggestions for improving the platform. This approach demonstrates their commitment to valuing feedback from their users and other involved parties. Additionally, YouTube uses its

¹¹ <https://music.apple.com/es/browse>

¹² <https://music.youtube.com/>

community webpage to announce the latest upgrades to its platform and any updates to its recommendation algorithm¹³.

Additionally, Pandora, Spotify, Apple Music and Deezer actively share news and updates to promote diversity among artists on their platforms. For example, Pandora has a monthly blog called '*The Listener Lounge*', where they feature weekly music picks and engage their community with questions. During specific months like February and March, they spotlight playlists featuring female¹⁴ or black artists¹⁵ and provide educational content to inform users about diversity.

Apple Music, on the other hand, also shares news about diversity¹⁶ but tends to focus on promoting services or products that support related organizations. While much of their news highlights new features or popular artists, they still try to promote diversity initiatives¹⁷.

Spotify maintains a news page that covers platform services and products, culture and trends, company culture, and interviews with artists and podcasters. This approach helps promote global diversity in music and fosters a sense of connection among stakeholders.¹⁸

Deezer also has a news page¹⁹ that posts about the latest company updates, including promoting diversity for women as well as other minorities. Their menu allows users to filter news based on their interests, making it easy to stay informed about research, platform updates, and music news.

Overall, these platforms show a strong commitment to culture and diversity as key parts of their company values. By engaging both users and artists, they create spaces where a variety of musical expressions are promoted and celebrated. Through different initiatives, educational content and targeted promotions, these companies highlight

¹³<https://support.google.com/youtubemusic/thread/176761070/changing-how-we-personalize-your-music-recommendations?hl=en>

¹⁴<https://community.pandora.com/t5/Community-Blog/The-Listener-Lounge-March-2024/ba-p/149650>

¹⁵<https://community.pandora.com/t5/Creators-Blog/Celebrating-Black-Musicians-Composers-and-Vocalists-in-Classical/ba-p/146879>

¹⁶<https://www.apple.com/newsroom/2023/01/apple-celebrates-black-history-month-with-unity-collection-and-exclusive-content/>

¹⁷<https://www.apple.com/newsroom/archive/apple-music/>

¹⁸<https://newsroom.spotify.com/news/>

¹⁹<https://newsroom-deezer.com/news/>

global music and ensure underrepresented voices are heard. This dedication to diversity enriches the listening experience and strengthens the connection between the platforms, their users and the artists.

To engage various stakeholders, Spotify has informative sites for artists²⁰, podcasters²¹, advertisers²², developers²³, investors²⁴, designers²⁵, engineers²⁶, vendors²⁷ and songwriters²⁸. These sites offer guidance on promoting products, improving user experience, and utilizing platform tools effectively. Similarly, Pandora offers a dedicated space for artists²⁹, allowing creators to share doubts, issues and valuable knowledge with each other. Apple Music also has an artist³⁰ page, focusing on how artists can upload music, edit their profiles, measure audience engagement and streams, and use other Apple products to enhance their music production.

These platforms collectively demonstrate their commitment to artists by offering resources and tools that support their music careers, helping them improve their craft, reach a wider audience and achieve professional growth.

As a final note, both Deezer and Spotify maintain highly active Research and Development (R+D) teams that regularly publish their latest research findings, as well as updates and revisions to their platforms³¹³². For instance, they recently announced details regarding a new royalty system.

Although we initially noted the limited availability of information about these platforms' recommendation systems in this subchapter, it's worth highlighting that Spotify and Deezer offer insights into their advancements and research conducted on their recommendation systems through their R&D websites. This is a form of dedication to

²⁰ <https://artists.spotify.com/home>

²¹ <https://podcasters.spotify.com/>

²² <https://ads.spotify.com/es-ES/>

²³ <https://developer.spotify.com/>

²⁴ <https://investors.spotify.com/home/default.aspx>

²⁵ <https://spotify.design/>

²⁶ <https://engineering.atspotify.com/>

²⁷ <https://spotifyforvendors.com/>

²⁸ <https://artists.spotify.com/songwriting>

²⁹ https://community.pandora.com/t5/Pandora-for-Creators-Community/gh-p/Pandora_for_Creators_Community

³⁰ <https://artists.apple.com/>

³¹ <https://research.atspotify.com/>

³² <https://research.deezer.com/>

transparency provides stakeholders with valuable insight into the platforms' ongoing progressions.

Spotify Search & Recommendation³³ research area focuses on enhancing user access to personalized audio content, including music and podcasts. The key objectives include improving recommendation algorithms, developing advanced audio search technologies and optimizing query analysis techniques. By prioritizing access to diverse content and personalized recommendations, Spotify aims to enhance user satisfaction and engagement while maximizing revenue generation through effective ad placement strategies.

Deezer's latest recommendation papers provide links to their code for free access, enhancing transparency within their platform³⁴. Based on their research in music recommendation systems, their main interests include the need for personalized and contextually relevant recommendations, such as utilizing temporal contexts and user-item interactions to improve recommendation precision and user experience. Additionally, they focus on providing more stable and insightful recommendations by exploring various recommendation methods using embedding techniques and matrix factorization. Their research also includes advancements in sequential recommendation systems through incorporating temporal contexts, addressing named entity recognition (NER) challenges and conducting human-centered evaluations (Afchar et al., 2023; Bendada et al., 2023; Epure & Hennequin, 2023; Tran et al., 2023).

In summary, the primary interests of music streaming companies, particularly Spotify and Deezer, regarding their RS are to enhance user experience by making it easier for users to discover personalized content and maximize their satisfaction. Both companies prioritize transparency in their research efforts, providing accessible insights and sharing their advancements in RS. Additionally, Spotify focuses on optimizing revenue by improving recommendation systems to enhance the effectiveness of ad placements. By addressing these objectives, these companies aim to improve and deliver a great user experience while maintaining transparency and maximizing their business potential.

³³ <https://research.atspotify.com/search-recommendations/>

³⁴ Example: <https://research.deezer.com/publication/2023/08/28/recsys-bendada.html>

2.3. Empirical Research on Multiple-Stakeholders in Music RS

In the research field of music RS, empirical research has made significant strides in understanding and addressing the multifaceted challenges posed by multistakeholder dynamics. These studies have not only shed light on the complexities involved but have also proposed innovative methodologies to enhance fairness, effectiveness and stakeholder satisfaction within the recommendation ecosystem.

Abdollahpouri and Burke (Ricci et al., 2022), have contributed a chapter that consolidates research on the involvement of multiple stakeholders in music recommender systems. The chapter underscores the importance of evaluating and modeling recommender systems (RS) from diverse stakeholder perspectives. Historically, RS research has predominantly focused on user-centric metrics such as accuracy, relevance and user satisfaction. However, adopting a broader evaluation framework becomes crucial for identifying and addressing potential disparities in system performance across various user subgroups. This approach ensures equitable and satisfactory outcomes for all stakeholders.

The chapter also highlights the challenges in this area, particularly the scarcity of real-world data that accurately reflects the interests and constraints of different stakeholders. Such data often include sensitive business information like supplier margins, platform commissions or demographic details distinguishing stakeholder groups. Collaboration is essential to access proprietary data, facilitating more realistic simulations and experiments that capture multistakeholder dynamics. For instance, previous studies have utilized diverse probability distributions to simulate supplier behaviors and model market conditions (Sürer et al., 2018), demonstrating the adaptability required in system design and evaluation.

In his PhD thesis, Abdollahpouri (Abdollahpouri H., 2020) investigates the challenge of popularity bias within recommender systems, particularly in multi-stakeholder environments. He critiques the current metrics used to evaluate music recommendation systems, noting that most are user-centered. These include Mean-Absolute Error (MAE) and Root-Mean-Square Error (RMSE), as well as ranking metrics like precision, recall,

and normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG). These metrics focus on how well the system ranks items to meet user preferences.

Abdollahpouri addresses popularity bias by presenting three different recommendation algorithms. The first is a model-based approach that builds on a learning-to-rank algorithm (RankALS). This method incorporates the popularity of recommendations into its objective function, aiming to diversify recommendations by penalizing lists that contain only popular or only long-tail items. Experimental results demonstrate that this method improves long-tail properties such as catalog coverage and long-tail coverage.

The second approach is a post-processing re-ranking method inspired by diversification techniques in information retrieval, like xQuAD. This method generates a larger list of recommendations and then re-ranks them to ensure fair representation of items from different categories. The experimental results show a significant improvement in the long-tail properties of recommendations, with only a minor loss in accuracy.

The third algorithm, called Calibrated Popularity, aims to ensure that recommendation lists for each user reflect the range of item popularity they originally showed interest in. For example, if a user's profile contains 20% popular items, 50% medium popularity items and 30% less popular items, the recommender system should maintain this ratio in its recommendations. Experimental results indicate that this approach not only better matches the distribution of recommendations to user profiles but also improves supplier fairness by equitably exposing items from different supplier groups.

Looking ahead, the thesis suggests several areas for further research. Conducting user studies to evaluate the proposed algorithms in real-world settings is essential, as it would provide insights into user interactions and perceptions of recommendations. Additionally, directly optimizing for supplier fairness by incorporating user tendencies towards different supplier groups and popularity categories into the calibration algorithm is another area of interest. Finally, exploring the connection between popularity bias and other types of fairness, such as gender, age and race, could offer a more comprehensive understanding of fairness in recommender systems.

The thesis also introduces metrics designed to evaluate multiple stakeholders in music recommendation algorithms, highlighting the need for a broader evaluative perspective, which are shown in the table below.

The following table shows the metrics proposed by Abdollahpouri for non-user evaluation:

Metric Name	Purpose	Formula
Aggregate diversity (Agg-Div)	The ratio of unique recommended items compared to all the available items.	$Agg - Div = \frac{ U_{u \in U} l_u }{ I }$
Average Percentage of Long-tail Items (APL)	The average percentage of long-tail items in individual recommendation lists.	$APL = \frac{1}{ U } \sum_{u \in U} \frac{ \{i, i \in (l_u \cap (M \cup T))\} }{ l_u }$
Long-tail Coverage (LC)	The percentage of long-tail items that are covered by the recommender system.	$LC = \frac{ U_{u \in U} (l_u \cap (M \cup T)) }{ M \cup T }$
Gini Index (Gini)	Measures how evenly the recommendations are distributed across all items.	$Gini(L) = 1 - \frac{1}{ I - 1} \sum_{j=1}^{ I } (2j - I - 1)p(i_j L)$

Table 1. Proposed metrics for non-user evaluation of music recommender systems for multiple-stakeholders architecture (Abdollahpouri H., 2020).

The parameters of the formulas for Table 1 are: U is the set of all users, l is the list of recommendations for a user, I is the set of all unique items, M is the set of mainstream or popular items, T is the set of items on the tail or less popular items, L is the list of recommendations, $p(i|L)$ is the ratio of occurrence of item i in the list L .

The next table shows the metrics proposed for supplier metrics:

Metric Name	Purpose	Formula
Equality of Attention Supplier Fairness (ESF)	Measures the fairness of exposure for different supplier groups based on the equality of appearance for different supplier groups.	$ESF = \sum_{i=1}^{ S } \sqrt{\sum_{j \in L} \mathbb{1}(A(j) \in S_i)}$
Supplier Popularity Deviation (SPD)	Measures the deviation of exposure for items from different supplier groups compared to their original popularity in data.	$SPD(s) = q(s) - p(s)$ $q(s) = \frac{\sum_{u \in U} \sum_{j \in l_u} \mathbb{1}(A(j) \in s)}{n \times U }$ $p(s) = \frac{\sum_{u \in U} \sum_{j \in \rho_u} \mathbb{1}(A(j) \in s)}{\sum_{u \in U} \rho_u }$ $SPD = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{ S } SPD(S_i) }{ S }$

Table 2. Proposed metrics for supplier evaluation of music recommender systems for multiple-stakeholders architecture (Abdollahpouri H., 2020).

The parameters of the formulas for Table 2 are: L is the list of recommendations, S is the list of suppliers belonging to popularity bin i , $A(j)$ is a mapping function that returns the supplier of item j , $q(s)$ is the ratio of recommendations that comes from items of the supplier group s , l_u is the set of items recommended to user u , $\mathbb{1}(A(j) \in s)$ is an indicator function that is 1 when item j belongs to the supplier group or 0 otherwise, n is the number of items recommended, U is the total number of users, $p(s)$ is the ratio of ratings that come from items of supplier s , ρ_u is the set of items that user u has rated or interacted with, S is the total number of suppliers.

The next table shows the metric proposed for user evaluation:

Metric Name	Purpose	Formula
Users Popularity Deviation (UPD)	Measures the average amount of deviation the algorithms impose on users in different groups compared to what their original interest in popularity was.	$UPD = \frac{\sum_{u=1}^{ U } UPD(U_i) }{ U }$

Table 3. Proposed metrics for user evaluation of music recommender systems for multiple-stakeholders architecture (Abdollahpouri H., 2020).

The parameters of the formulas for Table 3 are: U is the set of all groups, $|UPD(U_i)|$ ensures that deviations are treated equally regardless of direction.

The final table shows the metric proposed for item evaluation:

Metric Name	Purpose	Formula
Items Popularity Deviation (IPD)	Measures the deviation of exposure for items from different item groups compared to their original popularity in data.	$IPD(c) = q(c) - p(c)$ $q(c) = \frac{\sum_{u=U} \sum_{j \in R_u} \mathbf{1}(j \in c)}{n \times U }$ $p(c) = \frac{\sum_{u \in U} \sum_{j \in P_u} \mathbf{1}(j \in c)}{\sum_{u \in U} P_u }$ $IPD = \frac{\sum_{c \in C} IPD(c) }{ C }$

Table 4. Proposed metrics for item evaluation of music recommender systems for multiple-stakeholders architecture (Abdollahpouri H., 2020).

The parameters of the formulas for Table 4 are: $q(c)$ is the ratio of recommendations that come from item group c , U is the set of users, Ru is the set of recommended items for user u , n is the total number of recommendations, $\mathbf{1}(j \in c)$ is an indicator function that equals 1 if item j belongs to group c , $p(c)$ is the ratio of ratings that come from item group c , Pu is the set of items rated by user u , C is the set of item groups.

Other authors have also investigated this topic, C. Bauer and K. Dinnissen's exploration of fairness in MRS (Dinnissen & Bauer, 2022) underscores the critical need for equitable treatment across diverse stakeholder groups, including users and item providers such as artists. Their research identifies prevalent biases such as gender bias and popularity bias, revealing disparities in recommendation outcomes that impact both user satisfaction and artist exposure. By focusing on these biases, Bauer and Dinnissen highlight the foundational importance of fairness in ensuring balanced representation and enhancing the overall credibility of MRS.

Furthermore, M. Unger et al. (Unger et al., 2021) introduce a sophisticated framework leveraging neural network models to optimize conflicting objectives across users and artists. By employing a two-tower neural network architecture, this study aligns user engagement metrics with artist-centric goals such as expanding fan bases and reaching new listeners. Empirical evaluations conducted using proprietary datasets from Spotify demonstrate superior performance in achieving balanced recommendations, underscoring the efficacy of multi-objective optimization in real-world MRS applications.

Furthermore, Chaudhari et al. (Harshal A. Chaudhari, 2020) introduces scalable submodular optimization algorithms aimed at integrating seller coverage objectives with personalized recommendations. This approach ensures fair representation of item providers while maximizing utility for users, mitigating biases inherent in traditional recommendation systems. By emphasizing fairness alongside utility maximization, this framework sets a precedent for designing more inclusive and transparent recommendation algorithms that cater to the diverse interests and objectives of all stakeholders involved.

Collectively, these empirical studies contribute nuanced insights and methodological advancements to the evolving landscape of multistakeholder music recommender systems. By addressing biases, optimizing conflicting objectives and enhancing fairness, these research endeavors pave the way for future innovations aimed at creating more equitable, effective and lesser user-centric music RS. Integrating these findings can lead to the development of robust recommendation systems that not only meet the diverse needs of users and providers but also uphold fairness and integrity in recommendation practices across various domains.

3. Methods

This chapter outlines the methodological approach undertaken to address the first research question introduced in Chapter 1. It covers the selection and preprocessing of the dataset, the development of two distinct recommendation models and the metrics used to evaluate their effectiveness. The first model serves as a baseline by implementing a standard collaborative filtering technique, while the second model integrates advanced strategies aimed at enhancing diversity and promoting long-tail content. By evaluating these models using metrics such as Aggregate Diversity, Long-Tail Coverage and User Popularity Deviation, the chapter seeks to identify the optimal balance that meets the diverse needs and preferences of users, artists, and the platform.

3.1. Dataset

The dataset used for this research is the Last.fm HetRec 2011³⁵ (Cantador et al., 2011), which was released as part of the 2nd International Workshop on Information Heterogeneity and Fusion in Recommender Systems (HetRec 2011)³⁶. This workshop was held during the 5th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems (RecSys 2011)³⁷. The dataset was generated by the Information Retrieval Group at Universidad Autónoma de Madrid and is publicly available through the GroupLens research group³⁸.

This dataset includes information about 1.892 users, 17.632 artists, 12.717 bi-directional user friend relations, 92.834 user-listened artist relations (tuples of [user, artist, listeningCount]), 11.946 tags, 186.479 tag assignments (tuples of [user, tag, artist]).

This information is organized into five distinct files:

- **artist.dat** :
 - This file contains information about music artists listened and tagged by the users.
 - Data format: [id, name, url, pictureURL]

³⁵ <https://grouplens.org/datasets/hetrec-2011/>

³⁶ <http://ir.ii.uam.es/hetrec2011>

³⁷ <http://recsys.acm.org/2011>

³⁸ <https://grouplens.org/datasets/hetrec-2011/>

- **tags.dat :**
 - This file contains the set of tags available in the dataset.
 - Data format: [tagID, tagValue]
- **user_artists.dat :**
 - This file contains the artists listened by each user. It also provides a listening count for each [user, artist] pair.
 - Data format: [userID, artistID, weight]
- **user_taggedartists.dat - user_taggedartists-timestamps.dat :**
 - These files contain the tag assignments of artists provided by each particular user. They also contain the timestamps when the tag assignments were done.
 - Data format for **user_taggedartists.dat**: [userID, artistID, tagID, day, month, year]
 - Data format for **user_taggedartists-timestamps.dat**: [userID, artistID, tagID, timestamp]
- **user_friends.dat :**
 - These files contain the friend relations between users in the database.
 - Data format: [userID, friendID]

The choice of this dataset aligns with the multi-stakeholder architecture in music RS. The approach taken for each stakeholder is as follows:

- **Platform:** The dataset used in this research is derived from an online music discovery and recommendation service, Last.fm³⁹. This platform enables users to track their listening habits, discover new music and connect with other music enthusiasts. Two key considerations are relevant here:
 - **Algorithm Access:** Since we do not have access to Last.fm's proprietary recommendation algorithm, we cannot ensure that our implementation will produce recommendations identical to those generated by the platform. The lack of access to the platform's algorithm, which is typically kept private by companies for competitive and formal reasons, represents a limitation of our study.

³⁹ <https://www.last.fm/>

- **Dataset Authenticity:** The data used in this research is not directly extracted from the Last.fm platform. As discussed in Subchapter 3.1, the dataset was generated by the Information Retrieval Group at Universidad Autónoma de Madrid for the RecSys workshop in 2011. Consequently, we cannot expect the recommendations generated from this dataset to be as effective as those that might be produced using real-world data directly from the platform.
- **Artists:** The dataset provides basic information about the artists, including the artists themselves and the tags assigned to them by users. Since our focus is on a collaborative filtering model, we will not require any qualitative or quantitative information related to the specific songs or items that artists provide on music streaming platforms.
- **Users:** The dataset contains detailed information about users' listening habits, including the user-artist relationships and the number of times a user has listened to a particular artist. Additionally, it includes user-user relationships, specifically the friendship connections between users on the platform.

3.1.1. Data Preprocessing

To tailor the Last.fm HetRec 2011 dataset for the objectives of this research, we performed various data cleaning and preprocessing steps. These procedures, along with the algorithmic recommendation and evaluation, were executed using Python⁴⁰ within the Google Colab environment⁴¹.

For this study, all files listed in the dataset were utilized, with the exception of the **user_taggedartists-timestamps.dat** file, as the specific timestamp data is not required for the scope of our algorithmic recommendation research.

For the data preprocessing and cleaning steps, we began by extracting and importing all relevant files as Python Pandas data frames⁴². The initial step involved merging the

⁴⁰ <https://www.python.org/>

⁴¹ <https://colab.research.google.com/>

⁴² <https://pandas.pydata.org/docs/reference/api/pandas.DataFrame.html>

user_taggedartists and **user_friends** data frames using the common column *'userID'*. A left join was performed to maintain **user_taggedartists** as the primary data frame while incorporating the *'friendID'* column from the **user_friends** data frame.

The **user_taggedartists** data frame originally contained 186.279 rows, while the **user_friends** data frame had 25.434 rows. After merging, the resulting data frame expanded to 2.857.144 rows. This increase in row count is expected due to the structure of the data: each user in the **user_taggedartists** data frame is associated with multiple artists they have listened to, and each user can also have several friend relationships. Consequently, the merged dataset naturally becomes larger.

To simplify the merged dataset and facilitate more efficient analysis, we grouped the *'friendID'* column. Instead of having a separate row for each friend, we consolidated all friends of a user into a list within the *'friendID'* column. After performing this grouping, the dataset was reduced back to its original size of 186.279 rows, consistent with the **user_taggedartists** data frame.

Next, we merged the previously obtained data frame with the **tags** data frame using the common column *'tagID'*, once again doing a left join to preserve all the data from the merge data frame, which we will continue using until obtaining the final dataset. With this merge we incorporate the column *'tagValue'*, which provides the descriptive name corresponding to each *'tagID'*.

Subsequently, we merged the resulting data frame with the **user_artists** data frame using the common columns *'userID'* and *'artistID'*. This merge added the *'weight'* column, representing the number of times a user has listened to a particular artist. The *'weight'* serves as an important factor in the recommendation process, as a higher listening count (or weight) increases the influence of that artist in the recommendation algorithm..

The final merge involved the **artists** data frame, from which we selected only the columns *'id'* and *'name'*, as we wanted to incorporate the name of the artist to visualize better the recommendations. We renamed the column *'id'* to *'artistID'* to maintain

consistency and then merged this with the previously combined data frame on the on the common column *'artistID'*.

Our final dataset now includes all the necessary information, retaining a total of 186.279 rows, consistent with the original **user_taggedartists** data frame. This consistency was expected since we primarily added supplementary information to enrich the dataset for our music recommender system model.

The final preprocessing steps involved cleaning the data by replacing any NaN values with zeroes or empty strings, ensuring the dataset's integrity. The final data frame was then saved as a CSV file for further analysis.

In the following table, we present a sample of the initial rows from the final data frame that will be used in the next steps of this thesis research:

userID	artistID	name	weight	tagID	tagValue	day	month	year	friendID
0	2	52 Morcheeba	11690.0	13	chillout	1	4	2009	[275, 428, 515, 761, 831, 909, 1209, 1210, 123...
1	2	52 Morcheeba	11690.0	15	downtempo	1	4	2009	[275, 428, 515, 761, 831, 909, 1209, 1210, 123...
2	2	52 Morcheeba	11690.0	18	electronic	1	4	2009	[275, 428, 515, 761, 831, 909, 1209, 1210, 123...
3	2	52 Morcheeba	11690.0	21	trip-hop	1	4	2009	[275, 428, 515, 761, 831, 909, 1209, 1210, 123...
4	2	52 Morcheeba	11690.0	41	female vocalists	1	4	2009	[275, 428, 515, 761, 831, 909, 1209, 1210, 123...

Table 5. Final preprocessed data frame of the HetRec 2011 Last.fm Dataset

All the steps outlined in this section can be viewed in detail in the GitHub repository dedicated to showcasing the data preprocessing process⁴³.

3.2. Implementation for the First Simple Collaborative Filtering Model

The implementation was carried out as an offline experiment, a common approach for evaluating the effectiveness of recommender systems. However, it is important to note that this type of evaluation may not yield the highest quality recommendations, as it

⁴³

https://github.com/dianatyman/Collaborative_Filtering_Models_in_Music_RecSys_Enhancing_Diversity_Long-Tail/blob/main/Part1_Dataset_Preprocessing.ipynb

relies on a pre-collected dataset rather than real-time data from the actual world (Abdollahpouri, 2020).

Before diving into the detailed explanation of the first model's implementation, the following figure provides a simplified roadmap that outlines the methodology we followed. This visual guide will help clarify the steps involved in developing the model and how they interconnect.

Figure 3. Simplified Roadmap of the First Simple Collaborative Filtering Model

For the construction of the music RS, we focused on a single type of recommendation model: the Collaborative Filtering (CF) algorithm. Unlike typical RS that suggest individual songs, our system is designed to recommend artists. The main focus of this research will be how we can improve a standard music RS, where neither diversity nor the promotion of long-tail items is considered in the initial design. The goal is to create better recommendations that satisfy the different stakeholders involved, including users, artists and the platform.

The music RS is built using a matrix factorization technique using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) from the `scipy` library⁴⁴, which will be explained in detail later in this section. Before building the model with our dataset, several preprocessing steps were undertaken to better prepare the data. First, the *'weight'* values, representing the number of times a user has listened to an artist, were normalized using min-max normalization. This step was necessary because some of the original count values were too large, which could have skewed the model. Min-max normalization scales these values to a range from 0 to 1, using the formula:

$$X_{norm} = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}}$$

Where X represents the original *'weight'* values. After normalization, we grouped the `['userID', 'artist_name']` pairs to sum the weights of any duplicate rows, ensuring that each user-artist pair is uniquely represented in the dataset.

With the data prepared, we proceeded to use SVD to start building our model. SVD is a powerful matrix factorization technique widely used in collaborative filtering-based recommendation systems, including music RS. In these systems, the goal is to predict a user's preference for items (in this case, artists) based on their past interactions. These interactions are typically represented in a user-item interaction matrix, where each row corresponds to a user, each column corresponds to an item (artist), and the values in the matrix represent some form of interaction or preference, such as the number of times a user has listened to an artist. SVD helps in reducing the dimensionality of this matrix, enabling the system to identify underlying patterns in the data and make more accurate predictions.

In a collaborative filtering music recommendation system, the user-item interaction matrix is often sparse, meaning that most users have interacted with only a small subset of available artists. This sparsity poses a challenge for making accurate recommendations. SVD addresses this by decomposing the interaction matrix into three smaller matrices:

⁴⁴ <https://scipy.org/>

- U : Represents the users in a latent feature space.
- V^T : Represents the items (artists) in the same space.
- Σ : Is a diagonal matrix containing singular values that indicate the importance of each latent feature.

By projecting both users and artists into this shared latent feature space, SVD allows the recommendation system to infer a user's potential interest in artists they have not yet interacted with, based on the similarity of latent features. The parameter k in the SVD algorithm determines the number of latent features retained during the decomposition. A higher value of k captures more of the variability in the data but also increases the complexity of the model and the risk of overfitting. In our implementation, we selected ' $k=100$ ' to observe how this standard number of latent features would impact the quality of our recommendations.

After the decomposition, the interaction matrix is reconstructed by multiplying the three smaller matrices back together. This reconstructed matrix contains predicted interaction values for all user-artist pairs, including those that were originally missing in the sparse matrix. These predicted values represent how likely it is that a user will listen to an artist, even if they haven't done so yet.

This first model implementation includes a second part, apart of the SVD, as we wanted to take advantage of the information we have in the dataset, we wanted to include the social influence on the recommendations for each user. This involves not only considering a user's personal listening history but also taking into account the listening habits of their friends. By doing so, the system can make recommendations that are more socially aware, reflecting both individual preferences and the broader context of the user's social network.

The first step in incorporating social influence is to determine how much a user's friends might impact their music preferences. For each user, we start by identifying their friends within the dataset. We then filter out any friends who do not have sufficient interaction data, ensuring that we only consider those whose listening behavior is well-represented.

Once we have identified the relevant friends, we aggregate their listening behaviors to create a composite view of the music they collectively enjoy. This aggregated data represents the social influence for the user, indicating which artists are popular within their social circle. If a user has no valid friends in the dataset, we assume that their preferences are not socially influenced and proceed without adding any social factors.

After calculating the social influence for each user, the next step is to adjust the user's own listening data to reflect this influence. For each user, we add the aggregated listening preferences of their friends to their existing interaction data. This results in a new set of user preferences that combines both the user's personal listening history and the social trends within their network. Essentially, this step creates a more socially aware interaction matrix, where each user's preferences are shaped by both their individual tastes and the collective tastes of their friends.

With the socially adjusted interaction data in place, we proceed to generate music recommendations. This involves applying the SVD technique to the updated interaction matrix, which now includes social influence. By doing so, we can identify latent features that capture both individual and social aspects of music preferences.

The resulting model produces a set of predicted ratings for each user, which estimate how likely they are to enjoy various artists, including those they have not yet listened to. These predictions are now informed by a combination of the user's own listening history and the influence of their friends' preferences.

All the steps explained in this section are detailed in the GitHub repository created to showcase the implementation of the simple CF model⁴⁵.

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https://github.com/dianatyman/Collaborative_Filtering_Models_in_Music_RecSys_Enhancing_Diversity_Long-Tail/blob/main/Part2_CollabFiltering.ipynb

3.3. Implementation of the Second Enhanced Collaborative Filtering Model

The research for this thesis involves the development and evaluation of a second model aimed at enhancing a standard music RS by incorporating mechanisms to improve diversity and promote long-tail items, those that are typically underrepresented in conventional RS. This enhanced model seeks to address the needs of various stakeholders, including users and artists, by ensuring that the recommendations are not only relevant but also diverse and inclusive of lesser-known content.

Before proceeding to the explanation of the second model's implementation, the following figure presents a simplified roadmap outlining the methodology we followed:

Figure 4. Simplified Roadmap of the Second Enhanced Collaborative Filtering Model

For this implementation, we started by following the same steps as in the construction of the initial Collaborative Filtering (CF) model, with a key modification: increasing the number of latent factors from 100 to 700. This substantial increase in the number of latent factors was carefully managed to avoid overfitting. By closely monitoring the

model's performance, we determined that 700 was the optimal number of latent factors that could be used without compromising the quality of the recommendations..

In addition to adjusting the latent factors, we introduced a beta parameter to tune the influence of social factors on the recommendations. While improving diversity and promoting long-tail items are critical for both artists and users, it is equally important to ensure that the recommendations remain aligned with users' expectations. Simply recommending niche items for the sake of diversity could lead to dissatisfaction if those items do not resonate with the user. The social influence, therefore, plays a crucial role in balancing these objectives.

The beta parameter controls the extent to which a user's social circle (their friends) influences their recommendations. A lower beta value reduces the influence of friends, making the recommendations more aligned with a traditional CF model, where recommendations are based on the preferences of similar users who may not necessarily be in the user's social network. Conversely, a higher beta value increases the influence of friends, allowing the user's social circle to play a larger role in shaping their recommendations. For this model, we maintained the beta parameter at 0.5, a balance between these two influences.

Next we incorporate the new section into our model. We are including a diversification ranking, which after providing the top-15 recommendations for the users, it will apply algorithms like Maximal Marginal Relevance (MMR) to reorder the list to balance relevance with diversity. Furthermore, we will also incorporate an algorithm for long-tail promotion, to increase the chances of long-tail items being recommended by slightly boosting their scores.

Building on this foundation, we then incorporated two additional components to further enhance the model: a diversification ranking mechanism and a long-tail promotion algorithm. After generating the top 15 recommendations for each user, the diversification ranking mechanism reorders the list to balance relevance with diversity. This is achieved by applying the MMR algorithm, which selects items that are not only relevant to the user but also diverse from each other, thereby ensuring a more varied recommendation list. This is achieved using the formula:

$$MMR(i) = \lambda * Relevance(i) - (1 - \lambda) * \max_{j \in S} Similarity(i, j)$$

Where λ is a parameter that controls the balance between relevance and diversity, $Relevance(i)$ is the relevance score of item i and $Similarity(i, j)$ is the similarity between item i and each item j already selected in the set S .

Simultaneously, the long-tail promotion algorithm aims to increase the visibility of less popular items. These long-tail items, which typically fall into the bottom 20% in terms of popularity, are identified and their recommendation scores are slightly boosted. This adjustment increases the chances that these lesser-known artists will appear in the user's recommendation list, thereby promoting diversity and helping to introduce users to new and potentially overlooked content.

Finally, the model generates recommendations for all users by applying these enhancements. The interaction matrix, now enriched with social influence, is processed to produce a personalized list of recommendations for each user. These lists are then adjusted through the diversification and long-tail promotion mechanisms, ensuring that the final recommendations are not only aligned with the user's preferences but also contribute to a richer and more diverse music discovery experience.

Through this enhanced model, we aim to explore how diversity and long-tail promotion can be integrated into a recommendation system in a way that benefits all stakeholders, while still maintaining the quality and relevance of the recommendations.

All the steps explained in this section are detailed in the GitHub repository created to showcase the implementation of the enhanced CF model⁴⁶.

⁴⁶

https://github.com/dianatyman/Collaborative_Filtering_Models_in_Music_RecSys_Enhancing_Diversity_Long-Tail/blob/main/Part2_CollabFiltering.ipynb

3.4. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the performance of our algorithms, we selected the following metrics, which are detailed in Chapter 2.3:

- **Aggregate Diversity (Agg-Div):** This metric measures the ratio of unique recommended items compared to all available items in the catalog. It helps us understand how diverse the recommendations are across the entire user base. The formula used to compute this metric is as follows:

$$Agg - Div = \frac{|U_{u \in U} l_u|}{|I|}$$

This metric is important for our research because many recommendation algorithms tend to be biased towards popular items, resulting in low coverage (Celma & Cano, 2008) .

- **Long-Tail Coverage (LC):** The percentage of long-tail items that are covered by the RS. It ensures that the system is not just recommending the most popular items but also those from the long tail of the distribution. The formula used to compute this metric is as follows:

$$LC = \frac{|U_{u \in U} (l_u \cap (M \cup T))|}{|M \cup T|}$$

- **User Popularity Deviation (UPD):** This metric evaluates the average deviation in user preferences imposed by the algorithms, comparing the popularity of recommended items with the users' original interest in popularity. The formula used to compute this metric is as follows:

$$UPD = \frac{\sum_{u=1}^{|U|} |UPD(U_i)|}{|U|}$$

These metrics were also employed in Abdollahpouri’s doctoral dissertation (Abdollahpouri, 2020), where he applied them to various datasets and recommender systems within a multi-stakeholder architecture framework. His work demonstrated how these metrics can effectively measure the performance of recommendation algorithms, particularly in settings where the needs of multiple stakeholders, such as users, content creators, and platforms, must be balanced. While Abdollahpouri utilized these metrics alongside several others, as discussed in Chapter 2.3, our thesis will primarily focus on these three.

As discussed in Chapter 2, different stakeholders in a music RS have varying objectives, such as promoting diversity, ensuring fair representation of artists and providing high-quality recommendations to users. These goals guided our selection of the three key metrics: **Aggregate Diversity**, **Long-Tail Coverage**, and **User Popularity Deviation**. By focusing on these metrics, we aim to evaluate how effectively the music RS balances these competing interests, encouraging a wide variety of content, ensuring that both popular and niche artists are fairly represented and delivering personalized recommendations that align with individual user preferences. These insights will be critical in assessing the overall performance of our recommendation model, particularly in achieving the desired outcomes for all stakeholders.

4. Results

In this chapter, we present the results obtained from the evaluation of the two models implemented in this study. As detailed in the previous chapter, the first model is a basic Collaborative Filtering (CF) model that does not intentionally promote diversity or long-tail items. In contrast, the second model incorporates enhancements designed to improve diversity and promote long-tail items. The performance of each model was assessed using three key metrics: **Aggregate Diversity**, **Long-Tail Coverage** and **User Popularity Deviation**. These metrics were selected to evaluate how well the music RS balances the competing interests of various stakeholders, including users, artists, and the platform. The results provide insight into the effectiveness of the models in achieving these objectives.

4.1. Results for the First Simple Collaborative Filtering Model

The first model was evaluated on the three key metrics, and the results are as follows:

- **Aggregate Diversity:** 3,17%
- **Long-Tail Coverage:** 0,12%
- **User Popularity Deviation:** 132,59

The results for first model indicate a relatively low performance across all metrics. The **Aggregate Diversity** score of 0,0317 or 3,17% suggests that the recommendations generated by this model are not highly diverse, meaning the model tends to recommend a narrow subset of the available catalog. **Long-Tail Coverage** is also very low, at 0,0012 or 0,12%, indicating that the model predominantly recommends popular items and fails to adequately include less popular, long-tail items in its recommendations. The **User Popularity Deviation** score of 132,59 is relatively high, which suggests that the recommendations are biased towards items with high popularity, deviating significantly from the original preferences of users in terms of popularity.

Figure 5. Collaborative Filtering Model Results comparing the popularity of items before and after generating the recommendations

The corresponding histograms illustrating the distribution of item popularity in both the original and recommended sets are provided in the figure above.

- Distribution of Artist Popularity in Original Histogram:** This histogram shows how frequently each artist appears in the users' original interaction history. As expected, the histogram displays a steep drop-off, with a few artists being very popular and most artists having relatively few interactions, reflecting a typical long-tail distribution.
- Distribution of Artist Popularity in Recommendations Histogram:** This histogram shows the distribution of popularity for the artists recommended by the model. Here, the function calculates popularity based on how often each recommended artist appears across all user interactions in the dataset. The histogram indicates a strong concentration around the more popular items, confirming the model's bias towards recommending these artists. This further explains the low Aggregate Diversity and Long-Tail Coverage scores, as the recommendations do not extend far into the tail of less popular items.

4.2. Results for the Second Enhanced Collaborative Filtering Model

The second model introduced enhancements aimed at improving diversity and promoting long-tail items in the recommendations. The results are as follows:

- **Aggregate Diversity (Agg-Div):** 29,72%
- **Long-Tail Coverage (LC):** 7,68%
- **User Popularity Deviation (UPD):** 74,84

The second model demonstrates significant improvements over first model in all evaluated metrics. The **Aggregate Diversity** score increased to 0,2972 or 29,72%, indicating a broader and more diverse range of items being recommended to users. This improvement suggests that the enhancements made to the model, such as the introduction of social influence and diversification ranking, were effective in increasing the variety of recommendations.

The **Long-Tail Coverage** also saw a considerable improvement, rising to 0,0768. Or 7,68% This increase indicates that the second model is better at incorporating less popular, long-tail items into the recommendations, thereby offering users a wider array of content that goes beyond just the most popular choices.

Finally, the **User Popularity Deviation** score decreased to 74,84 , reflecting a reduction in the bias towards highly popular items. This decrease suggests that the recommendations generated by the second model are more aligned with the users' original preferences in terms of item popularity.

Figure 6. Collaborative Filtering Model with Diversity and Long-Tail Improvements Results comparing the popularity of items before and after generating the recommendations

The corresponding histograms for the second model provide visual confirmation of these improvements:

- Distribution of Artist Popularity in Original Histogram:** Like the first model, this histogram represents the original distribution of artist popularity within the user interaction data. The distribution remains consistent, showing the natural long-tail characteristic of the dataset.
- Distribution of Artist Popularity in Recommendations Histogram:** This histogram reveals a more even distribution of recommended items across different levels of popularity, showing that the second model successfully incorporated more long-tail items into the recommendations. However, a notable observation is the significant increase in long-tail item recommendations, which suggests that while the model is more diverse, it might have overemphasized these less popular items. This could indicate a potential over-boosting effect, which, while beneficial for diversity, might impact the fair representation of moderately popular artists and user satisfaction if not carefully balanced.

5. Conclusions

In this final chapter we will go through of the results stated in Chapter 4, go through some ideas for future work that could be added to this research and mention limitations of the project and finally, conclude the work done in this thesis.

5.1. Discussion of the Results

The results of this study provide a deep dive into the multi-stakeholder dynamics of music RS when modified to promote diversity and long-tail content. The enhancements made in the second model, which included the incorporation of social influence and diversification ranking, resulted in significant improvements in **Agg-Div** and **LC** metrics. These improvements suggest that the model was effective in addressing biases inherent in traditional CF approaches, leading to a broader and more inclusive set of recommendations. This is a particularly positive outcome for lesser-known artists, as it enhances their visibility in a crowded market, and for platforms aiming to diversify their content offerings.

However, the study also revealed the complexity of balancing diversity with user satisfaction. While the model successfully reduced the **UPD**, indicating some alignment with user preferences, the histogram analysis revealed a potential over-boosting of long-tail items. This overemphasis on niche content suggests that while the model succeeded in diversifying recommendations, it may have done so at the expense of relevance. This could result in recommendations that are less satisfying for users who prefer a mix of popular and niche content.

The challenge highlighted here is the need to find a balance where diversity and user relevance coexist. While promoting a more inclusive and diverse set of recommendations is ethically and commercially valuable, it should not overshadow the importance of personalized recommendations that resonate with individual user tastes. The balance between these two objectives is crucial for the overall effectiveness and acceptance of the music RS by all stakeholders, users, artists and platforms.

5.2. Future Work and Limitations

The insights gained from this research suggest several ideas for future work:

- **Exploration of Additional Metrics:** Future research should consider incorporating a broader range of evaluation metrics to provide a more comprehensive assessment of recommendation performance. Metrics that account for user satisfaction, artist exposure, and platform engagement could offer deeper insights into how well the system balances the diverse needs of stakeholders.
- **Integration of Real-World Data:** To increase the relevance and practical applicability of the findings, future studies should aim to integrate real-world interaction data from contemporary music streaming platforms. Access to real-time data would enable a more accurate evaluation of how diversity and long-tail promotion impact user engagement and artist representation in a live environment.
- **Stakeholder Feedback Incorporation:** A valuable direction for future research would involve directly gathering feedback from users, artists and platform. Incorporating qualitative feedback from these stakeholders could help refine the models to better align with their expectations and needs, leading to a more user-centered and artist-friendly recommendation system.
- **Refining Long-Tail Promotion:** Further work should focus on developing more sophisticated methods for promoting long-tail items that strike a better balance between diversity and user satisfaction. Techniques such as dynamic adjustment based on user feedback or more sophisticated multi-objective optimization strategies could be explored.
- **Expanding Stakeholder Analysis:** Future research could broaden the scope of stakeholder analysis to include additional groups, such as record labels, advertisers, and cultural institutions. Understanding the impact of recommendation algorithms on these groups could lead to the development of more comprehensive and equitable MRS designs that address the needs of all involved parties.

- **Application to Other Domains:** The approaches and insights from this study could be adapted and tested in other recommendation contexts, such as video streaming, e-commerce or news recommendations, to explore the broader applicability of diversity and long-tail promotion strategies. Additionally, future research should consider investigating biases related to gender, race and other aspects of fairness. By addressing these biases, it would be possible to develop more equitable recommender systems that better serve diverse user groups and content creators, ensuring a fairer and more inclusive experience across various domains.

5.2.1 Limitations

While this study provides some interesting insights into the design of music RS with a focus on multiple stakeholders, several limitations must be taken into account:

- **Data Constraints:** The research relied on the Last.fm HetRec 2011 dataset, which, although useful for this study, is not representative of current music consumption behaviors or the dynamics of modern streaming platforms. The dataset lacks real-time interaction data and critical platform-specific information, such as proprietary algorithms used by streaming companies. This absence limits the study's ability to fully replicate the decision-making processes and contextual factors that influence recommendations in real-world scenarios.

- **Algorithmic Overemphasis:** The second model's strong focus on promoting long-tail items, while effective in increasing diversity, may have led to an overrepresentation of niche content. This overemphasis underscores the challenges of fine-tuning algorithms to achieve a balance between diversity, relevance and fair representation for all artists.

- **Lack of Access to Proprietary Algorithms and Data:** The inability to access proprietary recommendation algorithms and detailed data from music streaming companies represents a significant limitation. This restriction hampers the ability to incorporate platform-specific factors that might significantly influence the effectiveness

and accuracy of the recommendations. Without these insights, the study's findings are somewhat constrained by the generalization of the algorithms used.

- **Computational Constraints:** The study was also limited by computational resources. More advanced models or higher computational power could have enabled the exploration of more complex algorithms and larger datasets, potentially leading to improved recommendation accuracy and better balancing of stakeholder needs.

5.3. Conclusions

This thesis set out to explore the modification of music RS to better serve the diverse interests of multiple stakeholders, users, artists and platforms, by promoting diversity and long-tail content. Through the development and evaluation of two models, this research aimed to demonstrate how such modifications could impact recommendation outcomes.

The study showed that incorporating social influence and diversification strategies into a simple CF model can significantly improve the diversity of recommendations and increase the visibility of long-tail content. These enhancements are beneficial for lesser-known artists, who gain more exposure, and for platforms that can offer a more varied content library to their users.

Moreover, the research demonstrated that while it is possible to reduce the bias towards popular content, this must be done carefully to avoid compromising the relevance and satisfaction of recommendations for users. The over-boosting of long-tail items in the second model highlighted the delicate balance required to maintain both diversity and user preference alignment.

In conclusion, this thesis achieved its primary goals as stated in the introduction. It provided a comprehensive analysis of how modifying MRS can benefit multiple stakeholders, highlighted the complexities involved in balancing these modifications, and offered insights into the trade-offs between diversity and relevance. The findings

contribute to the ongoing discourse on ethical and effective recommender system design, emphasizing the importance of stakeholder balance in achieving a fair and user-centered recommendation environment.

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